

Design of Experiment for Magnetorheological Damper using Taguchi Technique¹

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Abstract

The influential parameters which impacts on the performance of magnetorheological damper (MR damper) have been analyzed by design of experiment approach using Taguchi technique. Current(A), Displacement(mm) and frequency (Hz) were selected as the process input parameters and damping force as output parameter. The effect of Magnetorheological fluid (MR fluid) blended with TiO₂ and Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles on damping force have been observed in this research paper. Experimentation executed according to Design of Experiments (DOE) using Taguchi technique based on L16 Orthogonal array. ANOVA implemented to estimate the most influencing parameter. The results indicated that displacement is the most influential parameter followed by the current on the damping force of magnetorheological damper.

Keywords

Taguchi, DOE, ANOVA, MR Damper, MR Fluid, Nanoparticles.

1. Introduction

Magnetorheological fluid being smart material possess tunable properties. The properties of material are altered and reversed by the external parameters like frequency, current, amplitude or displacement and magnetic field as well. [1] Jacob Robinow discovered this interesting smart material in 1948 at the US National Bureau of Standard. Magnetic rheological fluid which is also termed as MR fluid is characterized by the simple and precise interface between the electrical power as input and the mechanical power as output. This property of MRF makes it a dynamic smart material and also attracts various industrial applications. The magnetorheological effect is useful in number of applications like

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valves, brakes, clutches and dampers. The damping force in case of MR damper depend upon the amount of current supplied, displacement and frequency as it is directly related with the magnetic field intensity induced in the damper.

The main objective of this paper is optimization of the parameters of magnetorheological damper so as to achieve the optimum damping performance. For this, the design of experiment (DOE) approach is followed [2]. It is an organized approach to find the effects of input parameters on output parameters. Also, it helps in optimization. It proves very helpful in experiment planning which offers statistical background required for analysis. R.A. Fisher, British statistician pioneered the application of statistical procedures to the design of scientific experiments. Design of experiments, suggests full factorial DOE that allows the set of possible factors. But large number of factors increases the number of experiments which in practice becomes time consuming and costly hence to avail limited number of experiments, Taguchi method of design of experiments being preferred.

Taguchi method is used to get the results of design of experiment systematically which selects the set of number of experiments from the available combinations. Taguchi has presented a systematic method that efficiently selects the set of experiments from all possible combinations which are useful to optimize the output economically in terms of performance and quality [2]. It uses orthogonal array which enables minimum number of experiments. Orthogonal array generally selected on the basis of cost of experiment and accuracy of the output results [3].

2. Materials & Methodology

2.1 Selection of MR Damper

Selection of suitable MR damper and MR fluid is essential from the point of view of experimentation in order to get successful results. Magneshox MR damper has been selected for the experimentation based on its mechanical and electrical specifications. It is linear type of damper having stroke length of 75mm. The damper has adjustable tension and compression mode with customized opening to fill the newly fabricated blend. Dampro+ MR fluid is selected for the experiment which is characterized by dark grey appearance with 2.45 g/cm^3 density. Both MR damper and MR fluid have been procured from ARUS MR TECH, Chennai, India.

2.2 Formation of MR Fluid Blend

In present research work, TiO_2 (Titanium Oxide) and Fe_3O_4 (Iron Oxide) nanoparticles are infused in magnetorheological fluid and blended in different proportions. It aims to offer better damping property with improved yield stress, viscosity and reduced sedimentation rate which makes it dynamic and effective for MR damper application. P.S. Paul, J.A. Iasanth et.al. in their research, proved that to get better damping capability TiO_2 nanoparticles magnetized with direct current at higher amplitudes offers better viscosity and reduces temperature in the MR fluid [4]. The effect of blending of TiO_2 and Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles is studied on magnetorheological fluid properties. TiO_2 & Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles with particle size (10–20, 30–50 nm) and purity 99.9% and 99.5% respectively are used for experimentation. The nano particles have been procured from Platonic Nanotech Private Limited, Jharkhand, India. The morphology of both particles sizes is nearly spherical. The quantity of TiO_2 and Fe_3O_4 added in

magnetorheological fluid obtained by following the MCDM technique, TOPSIS. TiO_2 0.2 weight % along with Fe_3O_4 1 weight % added with MR fluid 99.7 weight %.

While preparing blend, the weights of MR fluid and nanoparticles were calculated and taken in the measured quantity. It is followed by blending of nanoparticles with MR fluid. Mixture is then stirred and mixed homogeneously using ultrasonic bath sonicator. Prepared samples filled in 20ml glass vials and then were tested for physical and rheological properties. The density of prepared blend is 2.3 gm/cc^3 while sedimentation rate is 52%. The shear stress value is 49.52 Pa, Viscosity noted is 420.45 Pa and the magnetic flux density is 0.78 T.

3. Design of Experiment by Taguchi method

Taguchi experimental design is preferably used by the researchers to optimize the process parameters. It provides the precise number of experiments need to be conducted. Taguchi explains quality in the two parts viz; offline and online quality control [5]. It is considered as one of the most comprehensive statistical approaches in process developments. Taguchi method avails the use of unique design of orthogonal arrays to study the whole parameter space with a minimum number of experiments[6]. The Taguchi method uses a loss function to calculate the deviation between the experimental values and the desired values. This loss function is then converted into a signal–noise (S/N) ratio (g) [7] [8]. There are three kinds of quality characteristics in the analysis of the S/N ratio, namely the lower-the-better, the higher the-better, and the nominal-the-best [9][10]. For each of the process parameters, the S/N ratio is calculated based on the S/N analysis. The goal of this study was to maximize the damping force. Hence, the higher-the-better option is used here.

The steps involved in Taguchi design are as follows[5]

- a. Selection of the parameters to be optimized i.e., Problem statement finalization.
- b. Selection of the control parameters/factors i.e., input parameters which directly impacts the output variables.
- c. Selection of Taguchi Orthogonal Array.
- d. Allotment of factors and their interactions with the Orthogonal Array.
- e. Conduction of the experiment.
- f. Analysis of the data using S-N (signal-to-noise) ratio and ANOVA (Analysis of Variance)
- g. Prediction of the optimum performance.
- h. Perform the confirmation experiment.

In this research work, the design of experiment based on Taguchi method is developed with the aim of achieving maximum damping force of the damper. Therefore, the parameters or factors of the damper that impacts the damping force are considered.

3.1 Selection of orthogonal array and parameter assignment

Based on the literature survey, three critical parameters came out as current, displacement and frequency. The number of parameters and their interactions and the number of levels for the parameters are considered while selecting the L16 orthogonal array. This array is used in conducting the

optimization experiment. In order to evaluate the influence of these three critical damper parameters on the damping force, the experiments are designed and conducted by Taguchi methodology.

3.2 Selection of optimal levels for parameters - Minitab software is used for analysing the above response data and also to get the vital data regarding the model. To determine which factors are significantly affecting the response characteristics, i.e., damping force, analysis of variance (ANOVA) is carried out. The ANOVA summary and the percentage contribution of each parameter is tabulated in Table 5.

3.3 Experimental Details

Process parameters and their levels

Input parameter range is shown in Table 1. Current, displacement and frequency values have been mentioned with their levels.

Table 1 Input process Parameters and their range

Parameters	Units	Levels	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4
Current	A	4	0.5	1.0	1.5	2.0
Displacement	mm	4	1	2	4	6
Frequency	Hz	4	1	2	3	4

Orthogonal Array

Orthogonal array is obtained using Minitab software as shown in table 2. It is seen from Orthogonal Array and corresponding damping force values that, at higher current and higher displacement values, the higher magnitude of damping force is obtained. At 1 mm to 2mm displacement, actually force start generating.so damping force is not developed at that particular displacement. Hence, less magnitude of force is observed initially at 1 mm and 2 mm displacement.

Table 2 The L16 Orthogonal Array with a response parameter

Run	Current	Displacement	Frequency	Damping Force	SN RATIO
1	0.5	1	1	334	50.4749
2	0.5	2	2	429	52.6491
3	0.5	4	3	578	55.2386
4	0.5	6	4	799	58.0509
5	1	1	2	570	55.1175
6	1	2	1	706	56.9761
7	1	4	4	1068	60.5714
8	1	6	3	1097	60.8041

9	1.5	1	3	540	54.6479
10	1.5	2	4	1028	60.2399
11	1.5	4	1	943	59.4902
12	1.5	6	2	1179	61.4303
13	2	1	4	643	56.0828
14	2	2	3	1009	60.0778
15	2	4	2	1119	60.9766
16	2	6	1	1035	60.2988

In order to obtain optimum level, SN ratio of each parameter level should be assessed. SN ratio combines mean and variance. It measures the response variation relative to nominal value under different noise condition. Three approaches of SN ratio are available viz; Larger is better, Nominal is best and Smaller is better. In this research work, the Larger is better approach is used to calculate SN ratio as we aim to achieve the maximum damping force with the given inputs of current, displacement and frequency. The formula used to calculate the SN ratio for Larger is better approach is as described below.

$$\frac{S}{N} = -\log \frac{1}{n} \left(\sum \frac{1}{y^2} \right)$$

Where “n” indicates number of responses in the factor level combination and “y” indicates the responses for the given factor level combination.

Table 3 Response Table for Signal to Noise Ratios

Level	Current (A)	Displacement (B)	Frequency (C)
1	54.10	54.10	56.81
2	58.37	57.49	57.54
3	58.95	59.07	57.69
4	59.38	60.15	58.76
Delta	5.28	6.04	1.95
Rank	2	1	3

Table 4 Response Table for Means

Level	Current (A)	Displacement (B)	Frequency(C)
1	535.0	521.8	754.5
2	860.3	793.0	824.3

3	922.5	927.0	806.0
4	951.5	1027.5	884.5
Delta	416.5	505.8	130.0
Rank	2	1	3

Here, A4B4C4 indicates optimum combination for SN ratio as well as means. From response table of SN ratio and means, it is clear that here displacement is ranked 1 and indicated as influencing parameter. The reason being at higher displacement of piston in the damper, the larger values of damping force are obtained. At 1 and 2mm displacement the damping force just start to develop inside the damper. Still the higher values of damping force, developed at maximum current values i.e., 1.5 A, 6mm displacement and frequency 2Hz. The damping force developed in the damper is directly proportional to the current.

Fig.1 Plot for SN Ratios and Means

From SN ratio and Means graphs, it is clear that displacement is the influencing parameter in MR damper. Second influencing parameter is current and frequency is next to that.

ANOVA – Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) is a statistical method which is used to determine the individual interactions of all the control factors in the test design. In present research work, ANOVA is used to analyse the effects of current, displacement and frequency on damping force. The significance of control factors in ANOVA is determined by comparing the F values of each control factor.

The last column of the table shows the percentage value of each parameter contribution which indicates the degree of influence on the process performance. In the analysis, R² value is 93.24% which is good one. And R² adjacent value is 83.10%. Both the values are on positive side.

Table 5 Complete ANOVA Results summary

Source	Degrees of Freedom (DF)	Sum of Squares (SS)	Contribution	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
A-Current(A)	3	442459	39.15%	442459	147486	11.58	0.007
B-Displacement(mm)	3	576634	51.03%	576634	192211	15.09	0.003
C-Frequency (Hz)	3	34543	3.06%	34543	11514	0.90	0.492
Error	6	76410	6.76%	76410	12735		
Total	15	1130045	100.00%				

S	R-sq	R-sq(adj)	PRESS	R-sq(pred)	AICc	BIC
112.850	93.24%	83.10%	543363	51.92%	268.95	211.45

Regression Analysis

Regression is a statistical modelling process which establishes relation among dependent (response) and independent variables (input parameters or predictor). Regression can be modelled as linear and in polynomial relationships. The most common regression is linear regression, for which an investigator finds the linear function that most closely close to the data

R² value which indicates coefficient of determination of the equations obtained by linear regression model were found to be 93.24%. It shows good level of relationship between dependent and independent variables. Regression equation is as follows. Based on the given input values of current, displacement and frequency the regression equation of output i.e., damping force is obtained.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Dampin g Force} = & 817.3 - 282.3 \text{ Current}_{0.5} + 42.9 \text{ Current}_{1.0} + 105.2 \text{ Current}_{1.5} + 134.2 \text{ Current}_{2.0} \\ & - 295.6 \text{ Displacement}_1 - 24.3 \text{ Displacement}_2 + 109.7 \text{ Displacement}_4 \\ & + 210.2 \text{ Displacement}_6 - 62.8 \text{ Frequency}_1 + 6.9 \text{ Frequency}_2 - 11.3 \text{ Frequency}_3 \\ & + 67.2 \text{ Frequency}_4 \end{aligned}$$

Fig.2 Residual plots for damping force

Residual plots for damping force are as shown in the figure.

Normal probability plot of residuals indicates the residuals versus expected values. It should follow approximately a straight line. The scatter of points is dispersed the way explaining the linear model is appropriate.

Histogram of the residual indicates the distribution of the residuals for all the observations.

Residual versus fit graph plots the residuals on y-axis and fitted values on x-axis. The points seen falling randomly on both sides of zero which shows the fall of fitted values is promising.

Residuals versus order shows the residuals in the order that the data were collected. The residuals on the plot seen falling randomly above and below the centre line indicating the coherence in the bservations.

Confirmation Test

In Taguchi analysis, the final step is to predict and verify the improvement of the response using the optimal level of process parameter.

Confirmation tests are carried out to validate the experimental results and to evaluate the accuracy of the analysis. The optimum combination of SN ratio and means is observed at A4B4C4. SN ratio for the same is indicated in table 6. In experimentation, the readings were taken at optimal values. The experimental optimal value is close to the predicted value. It means that the predicted value confirms with the experimental values.

Table 6 Results of Confirmation Test

	Predicted Optimal Result	Experimental Result
Level	A4B4C4	A4B4C4
S/N Ratio (Damping)	62.865	61.471

4. Results & Discussions

The analysis of variance (ANOVA) has been used to distinguish the significant factors from insignificant ones. The mean and S/N ratios were used in the statistical evaluation.

Fig. 1 & 2, shows the main effects of the parameters for S/N ratios for each level of the parameters. The average S/N ratio values, calculated for each factor at a given level, allow the establishment of the best levels.

Analysis is based on, the larger the S/N ratio, the better the response. It was found that the best parameters combination and their levels are A4B4C4. Value of Current at A4 level 59.38, Displacement at B4 level 60.15, Frequency at C4 level 58.76 which indicates that displacement is the most influential input parameter to the output damping force.

F value for displacement is found to be higher than current and frequency.

R^2 values of the equations which were obtained by linear regression model were found to be 93.24%. Predicted Optimal value is 62.8646 and experimental value is 61.471. The experimental optimal value is nearby to the predicted value. Hence, the predicted value confirms with the experimental values.

5. Conclusion

In this Design of Experiment using Taguchi method, the best combination is obtained at A4B4C4 level of current, displacement and frequency of which the displacement of the damper proved the most influential parameter in this work. R^2 values of the equations were found to be 93.24%. Predicted optimal value is 62.865 and experimental value is 61.471. Hence, it could be concluded that the predicted result is confirming with experimental results.

Declaration of competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper

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